

A case series of PLACENTA ACCRETA SYNDROME, Management and complication

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ABSTRACT:

Background: Placenta accreta spectrum is a life-threatening condition of abnormal invasion and adherence of placental villi to the myometrium. PAS is associated with very high maternal morbidity and mortality and requires a multidisciplinary approach with all the expertise to reduce adverse outcomes. **Method:** Here, we are discussing management of the PAS cases over 2years (December 2022 to December 2024) in Koppal institute of medical sciences. We have discussed the cases, mode of diagnosis, management and procedure done, intraoperative complications faced, management of the complications and postoperative prognosis of the patients. **Result:** patients were managed based on intraoperative findings, interventions and prognosis noted. **Conclusion:** Placenta accreta syndrome is increasing as the rate of caesarean section is increased, proper antenatal follow ups and high level of suspicion in previous LSCS cases and timely Ultrasound and MRI in indicated cases.

Keywords: *Placenta accreta spectrum, myometrium, PAS, Ultrasound and MRI*

INTRODUCTION:

Placenta accreta syndrome (PAS) is a potentially life-threatening condition characterized by abnormal placental attachment to the uterine wall. It encompasses a spectrum of disorders, including placenta accreta, increta, and percreta, which differ based on the degree of placental invasion into the myometrium or beyond the uterine serosa.¹ The condition is typically associated with significant maternal morbidity and mortality due to the risk of massive hemorrhage during delivery. The incidence of PAS has increased in recent years, largely due to the rising rates of cesarean deliveries and advanced maternal age, both of which are considered key risk factors.² Early recognition and appropriate management are critical to improving outcomes, with preoperative imaging, such as ultrasound and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), playing a crucial role in diagnosis. Despite advancements in prenatal detection and surgical techniques, PAS remains a major obstetric challenge, requiring multidisciplinary care involving obstetricians, anesthesiologists, and neonatologists.^{3,4} In this publication, we will review the pathophysiology,

risk factors, diagnostic strategies, and management approaches for PAS, with a focus on the latest research findings and clinical practices.⁵

METHODS: We are discussing PAS cases found in Koppal institute of medical sciences, how the cases presented with intraoperative management with prognosis and types of complications associated with it.

CASE: 1

G3P2L2 30y 35week+5d Prev 2 LSCS placenta previa and accreta, C/O PV bleed, conservative management with dexona coverage done, taken for elective LSCS, adhesion noted to bladder base, placenta percreta noted, torrential bleeding present after extraction of baby, massive blood transfusion done, internal iliac artery ligated and hysterectomy done, Adhered placenta @ bladder base left insitu, massive blood transfusion done, patient was intubated and on inotropes, and was discharged on POD 22 followed by DJ stenting due to ureter injury.

CASE: 2

29-year old G3P2L2 A1 37-week 1 day, with previous 2 LSCS, with placenta previa, came with c/O PV bleed, Emergency LSCS taken, placenta percreta noted and adherent to bladder base, torrential bleeding present after extraction of baby, hysterectomy done and multiple blood transfusion done, bladder injury repaired, patient was on inotropes, was started on methotrexate and serial USG done, and was discharged on POD 10.

CASE: 3

A 32-year old G4P2L2 A3 with 36-week 3 day with previous 2 LSCS c/O PV bleed came in labor, antenatally diagnosed as accreta, by USG, Taken for Emergency LSCS, intractable bleeding noted after extraction, hysterectomy done and multiple blood transfusion done, patient was shifted to ICU and discharged on POD 5

CASE: 4

A 28-year old G2P1L1 35-week 5d previous LSCS with placenta previa came with c/O PV bleed and pain abdomen, taken for emergency LSCS, after extraction of baby, placenta separated partially, and bleeding was more, hysterectomy with multiple blood transfusion done, patient vitals stable, shifted to wards.

CASE: 5

A 32-year old G7P6L2 with 34+2 weeks POG with previous 2 LSCS was admitted in view of her antenatal scan showing complete placenta previa with percreta, with FGR, for safe confinement. Upper segment Cesarean section done. Due to severe hemorrhage, hysterectomy was done.

CASE: 6

A 34-year old G2P1L1 30-week 4day previous 1 LSCS, With complete placenta previa a came with PV bleed and taken for emergency LSCS and found out placenta was invading the myometrium, Placenta left in situ, started on inj methotrexate, patient developed fever and endometritis, started on higher antibiotics, with serial scans, eventually it resolved, patient became symptomatically better

Complications:

PPH and major transfusion support-5 cases (83.33%),
Caesarean hysterectomy-5 cases (83.33 %)
ICU admission in 5 -83.33%
Fever in 1 case (16.66%) and
Bladder injury in 2 cases (33.33%)

DISCUSSION:

Therefore, all the cases had a high-risk factor, thus emphasizing the need to carefully evaluate the placental implantation site at the time of routine ultrasound and

also the need to maintain a high index of suspicion in cases bearing high risk factors. Antenatal diagnosis of placenta accreta spectrum is crucial in planning its management and has been shown to reduce maternal morbidity and mortality. [RCOG, Green top guidelines New 2018]. All the patients required 3-6 units of blood transfusion and component therapy. 4 patients required ICU stay, in view of hypovolemic shock requiring mechanical ventilator+/- ionotrope support. 3 patients had prolonged hospital stay, 2 in view of bladder injury, 1 patient in view of expectant management who later developed fever. Histopathological examination in all cases, confirmed diagnosis of Placenta Accreta. The reported complications associated with PA are- PPH and massive blood transfusion, cesarean hysterectomy, Bladder injury, ICU admission, fever and endometritis. Major risk factors for placenta accreta are placenta previa and previous cesarean section.

Diagnosis:

Color flow doppler ultrasound – early detection- 2nd trimester:

Women with a history of previous caesarean section seen to have an anterior low-lying placenta or placenta praevia at the routine fetal anomaly scan should be specifically screened for placenta accreta spectrum. [RCOG GREENTOP GUIDELINES, New 2018] Grade of recommendation: D

On USG:

Loss of normal hypoechoic space between placenta and urinary bladder or serosa
Visible sonoluscent spaces within the placenta, adjacent to the uterine walls- placental lacunae
Persistent blood flow between the basal placenta and myometrium revealed on color doppler.

Magnetic Resonance Imaging:

MRI may be used to complement ultrasound imaging to assess the depth of invasion and lateral extension of myometrial invasion, especially with posterior placentation and/or in women with ultrasound signs suggesting parametrial invasion.

In unsuspected cases of emergency LSCS, diagnosis can be made when there is difficulty establishing a cleavage plane during removal of placenta. If the placenta separates, the placenta needs to be delivered if it begins to separate. Any haemorrhage that follows, needs to be managed in the normal way. If the placenta partially separates, the separated portion(s) should be delivered and any haemorrhage that occurs should be dealt with.

Adherent segments can be left in place, but blood loss in such circumstances can be large and management of massive haemorrhage should follow without delay. Management: Time of delivery- In the absence of risk factors for preterm delivery, 35+0 to 36+6 weeks of gestation provides the best balance between fetal maturity and the risk of unscheduled delivery. Planned Caesarean section

Consent- risk of massive hemorrhage, lower urinary tract injury, need for blood transfusion, hysterectomy

Multidisciplinary team:

Caesarean section in suspected placenta previa, accrete:

Open the uterus at a site away from the placenta Deliver the baby without disturbing the implantation site in order to enable conservative management of the placenta or elective hysterectomy.

Entering the uterus through the placenta in order to achieve delivery is associated with more bleeding and a high chance of emergency hysterectomy After fetal delivery, the extent of placental invasion is assessed without attempts at manual placental removal.

Uterus preserving surgery:

In unsuspected cases, temporarily to transfer patient to a higher level of care To preserve fertility

Appropriate when:

- the extent of the placenta accreta is limited in depth and surface area,
- the entire placental implantation area is accessible and visualised i.e. completely anterior, fundal or posterior without deep pelvic invasion

CONCLUSION:

Placenta accreta is an obstetric challenge that is increasing in frequency and is associated with huge maternal mortality and morbidity. Clinicians should be aware of the clinical issues, risk factors, and imaging findings associated with placenta accreta to facilitate optimal case management. Scheduled cesarean hysterectomy performed under controlled circumstances, without any attempt at removing the placenta, availability of adequate transfusion support, multidisciplinary team, significantly reduce maternal morbidity and mortality.

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